

Gender Equality
GE ACADEMY

D7.3 Dissemination, communication and stakeholders' engagement activities progress report version 2 (VIL)

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Deliverable 7.3: Dissemination, communication and stakeholders' engagement activities progress report version 2

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1. Executive Summary

The GE Academy project develops and implements a high-quality capacity-building programme on gender equality in research, innovation and higher education. The capacity-building programme is based on state-of-the-art knowledge and composed of a series of tailor-made training materials and different training formats (including: In-person trainings, Summer Schools, Physical Interactive workshops, Webinars, Distributive Open Collaborative Courses (DOCCs), Train-the-Trainer sessions). At the same time, a pan-European network of gender trainers, both female and male, is under establishment so as to train, practitioners and researchers are trained, coached and upskilled for delivering gender training sessions tailored to the Research & Innovation (R&I) and Higher Education (HE) communities all over Europe and beyond. The programme is executed in more than 15 countries addressing the broad spectrum of topics concerned and supporting the 'mainstreaming' of gender expertise in different disciplinary areas and scientific fields, which will implicitly spread gender perspectives and gender dimensions in various organisations. Avoiding a simplistic and binary vision of gender, the approach takes intersectionality into account, meaning the interlocking, complex system of inequalities and differences in which individuals are embedded.

In this respect, the key for the achievement of the ambitious objectives of GE Academy is the implementation of the highly effective dissemination, communication and stakeholders' engagement strategy (D7.1) that ensures:

- The wider promotion and outreach of the project to critical stakeholders to speed up its wider use and impact on the economy and the society.
- The communication of the benefits and opportunities offered through our programmes and activities.
- The engagement and involvement of key stakeholders in the project's activities.
- The development and sustainability of the overall project and the pan-European network of gender trainers and other relevant stakeholders.
- The exploitation of the project results and the sustainability of the proposed activities and overall approach.

The outbreak of COVID-19 has caused an interruption in the work under WP4 and WP5 and the need for mitigation planning that required all involved partners' immediate attention and time. Considering the forced postponement of the delivery of in-person sessions due to COVID-19 and the uncertainty about the duration of this period, the partners have decided to prioritise the development (and delivery) of online sessions which caused adjustments to the online campaigns and the promotion of the GE Academy capacity-building programme in the era of online sessions which increased the competition.

This report is the second interim version of D7.1 "Dissemination, communication and stakeholders' engagement strategy". The first interim version was developed during M12 and the last one will be submitted to the EC by the end of the project.

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This deliverable provides an overview of the activities conducted during the second year of the project (M13-M24). It describes the progress and statistics of the communication activities (online and offline) including the project website, social media channels, newsletters, videos, press releases, third-party events and attempts to indicate any changes or improvements in relation to the initial strategy and plan. It is essential to mention that during this project period efforts were focused on the roll-out of the capacity-building programme following the adjustments that resulted from the pilot testing of the first year and the adjustments that resulted from the covid-19 pandemic.

2. Introduction

This document presents the updated dissemination and communication strategy of the project, focusing on making some particular dissemination channels and tools (especially the online ones) more effective to reach a wider audience for the roll-out of the GE Academy programme, to continue disseminating this programme to relevant target groups and stakeholders across Europe and beyond. This is also the progress report presenting the communication achievements of GE Academy (M13-M24).

In particular, GE Academy tools and activities include both online and offline:

- A dedicated project website (<https://ge-academy.eu/>) allowing for fast and easy communication of the most relevant information and news to a broad audience and to the appropriate target groups looking for opportunities to receive gender training.
- Social media channels ([Facebook](#), [Twitter](#), [LinkedIn](#) page, [LinkedIn](#) private Alumni/ae group) to communicate the activities and value of the project.
- A [YouTube channel](#) for the purpose of presenting the “Webinars’ series on Gender Equality in Research and Innovation” and any other recorded video and session of GE Academy.
- Newsletters and press releases to inform relevant stakeholders about the key achievements of the GE Academy project and next activities planned.
- Participation in external events and organisation of dedicated sessions with the main purpose of getting potential stakeholders directly involved in the network but also for gathering feedback about the activities performed by the Consortium.
- Coordination with relevant projects towards joint dissemination efforts and online accounts on popular GE platforms ([Eurogender](#), [GenPORT](#)).
- Printed and online material.
- Various other activities and tactics.

The project communication and dissemination tools and activities are being reviewed and updated on a regular basis for assessing new and possible dissemination opportunities that emerge during the project implementation. The updated strategy was conceived after the internal review of the dissemination activities and was designed given the beginning of the roll-out implementation phase. It was tailored to fit the project time plan and the current uncertain situation with the pandemic.

2.1 Intended Audience

This document aims to be a practical tool for the project’s communication manager as well as for all project partners to efficiently develop their individual and collective dissemination and communication activities and contribute to the overall objectives of the project. It provides the reader with all relevant information around the dissemination of the project, with ways to verify the implemented actions.

2.2 Document structure

This introduction is followed by a presentation of the updated dissemination and communication strategy (section 3). The subsequent section 4 is dedicated to the reporting of the activities conducted during year 2 (M13-M24). In addition, section 5 provides the progress in numbers and the overall monitoring approach of the communication activities. Lastly, section 6 provides a few conclusions and lessons-learnt for the forthcoming period.

3. Updated Dissemination and Communication Strategy

This section provides a short overview of the projects dissemination and communication strategy as presented in D7.1 Dissemination, communication and stakeholders' engagement strategy together with some important updates that were decided among partners in order to make the overall dissemination activities more effective towards the promotion of the roll-out programme according to the suggestions made via the interim project review (June 2020), the online consortium meeting (October 2020) and the continuous discussions and monitoring of the Project Management Team online meetings.

A set of changes and updates are shortly presented here:

- Communication and dissemination Tools and Channels: Particular emphasis was given to the project website by improving the online content with the initiation of the roll-out. In addition, extra efforts were dedicated to social media and a stronger link with partners' social media and online accounts and sister projects accounts was established.
- Visual identity: to avoid the simplistic and binary use of blue and pink, the visual identity of the project was updated and enriched with more colours appealing to the eye and matching the initial visual identity of the project logo. Light grey and purple were added to the canva of the visuals for optimal content representation.
- Reporting and Evaluation: More systemic reporting and evaluation activities among partners.

3.1 Project website

Among the tools employed to disseminate GE Academy, it was agreed that emphasis should be given to the improvement of the project's website and promotion activities in social media. Moreover, due to the release of the webinars series' and the provision of uploading and making available a few online sessions, a YouTube channel was developed and communicated to support their dissemination. Various suggestions were presented throughout the year, and partners agreed to implement the following changes:

- Insert an "open calls" section on the front page to advertise the upcoming sessions.
- Update and enrich the individual pages of the different training sessions when registration/application period is opened to specify the target groups, the objectives and highlight the agenda and the trainers/speakers involved.
- Make past sessions easily accessible with the creation of the "past training" page.
- Add a Frequently Asked Questions page on the menu for popular inquiries.
- Update the project calendar.
- Update the icons of the training offer with more appealing ones.
- Update several pages with more information.

As a result, the website has a fresher look and it is able to provide the correct information in a few clicks. Below, we present a few details about its new pages that are not included in D7.2.

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Figure 1. Website – Training offer preview

Figure 2. Training offer updated icons

Past training (<https://ge-academy.eu/past-training/>): This section contains links to past training sessions. It provides an overview of the completed sessions and the programme.

Training offer (<https://ge-academy.eu/gender-trainings>): This section is mainly dedicated to provide information about what gender trainings are, who they are for, how you can register/apply etc. This page includes direct links to other pages based on the format. It acts as a key entry point of information and it is highlighted in the homepage.

Calendar (<https://ge-academy.eu/calendar>): This section is dedicated to providing information about training opportunities, including the links to enroll, the specific dates, etc. At this point, it is in a starting stage and it will be developed by the beginning of January to reflect the roll-out programme.

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Frequently Asked Questions (<https://ge-academy.eu/faq/>): containing answers to frequently asked questions about our training sessions.

Deliverables (<https://ge-academy.eu/deliverables/>): the approved by the EC public deliverables are published.

Project resources (<https://ge-academy.eu/resources/>) containing completed webinars, useful material, media kit, deliverables, other project resources made available to public.

3.2 Social media and online channels

Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn

Social media channels are being used as described in D7.1 with a few examples below. Messages are tailored to the characters and length permitted by each channel, while images are being used and relevant partners and accounts are being tagged to reshare the posts.

Figure 3. Implementation of a social media campaign – Examples per channel

To enhance any promotional efforts, joint campaigns were organized with sister projects and relevant initiatives, while relevant hash tags were used e.g. #UnionofEquality. In addition, the live blogging element was particularly used during the webinars to post highlights of the session and motivate participants to post about their impressions and views. Tags were also frequently used with the accounts of the European Commission, relevant DGs with organizational accounts

Except for communication through partners accounts, cross-posting is recommended to host institutions, speakers/trainers of the training sessions to ensure a wide spread of the word about the sessions. VIL is in contact with them to advise and learn the different opportunities for the most effective promotion.

YouTube channel

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YouTube channel (<https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCGLibmdaDB8TPMRIFUfDiNQ>) was created to cover the need of publishing the project videos. So far, ten (10) videos have been published, while most of them have been promoted along with the channel itself. The main aim of the channel developed is to showcase the webinars while attracting high quality participants for our next set of activities and acting as a repository for future reference. More videos will be added as some of the sessions that were shifted online due to the pandemic have been recorded. A header to promote the channel has been developed and all the videos have aligned covers and description which includes the objectives of the session, the speakers and the specific timing of their part.

Figure 4. YouTube Channel

3.3 Material developed and visual identity

The development of the GE Academy branding was a key priority from the beginning of the project in order to create a single visual identity and make it easily identifiable by the target audiences. All project material developed includes in a prominent position the EU Funding visibility.

The branding pack for the roll-out programme prepared by VIL and it is used by all project members and relevant actors and includes:

- Social media images - promotional templates
- Agenda template for the training sessions
- Template for trainer's presentation
- Script template
- Handout template
- Certificate of attendance

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Most of the abovementioned material is being used by the host institutions of different training sessions to run local promotion and they are tailored to each individual purpose, audience and session according to the needs indicated by the host organisation in cooperation with VIL, relevant partners and the careful evaluation from YW. Those material are being presented in D7.2 and their updates in terms of colours and design are below:

Social media images - promotional templates

These templates have been developed to facilitate the promotion of the sessions to a wider audience and boost the accompanying messages on different online platforms by offering a quick set of important information including the topic of the session, the format, the date, the location and the message that registration is open.

Figure 5. Social media image – promotional template progression

Agenda template for the training sessions

Another important template for the promotion of the training sessions is the one containing the agenda and the overview of the training, thus delivering information about the actual content of the session.

Figure 6. Training session – Agenda template progression

4. Reporting on Communication and Dissemination activities (M13-M24)

4.1 Project website

The project website is used as one of the main communication and dissemination tools of the project. During the second year of the project, we used the project's website to:

- Provide information about the project and help stakeholders understand why they might want to get involved and how they can participate in the project's activities and use its results.
- Provide information as a central point for the available training sessions.
- Make available the available project outputs.
- Publish the project news.
- Publicise the project dissemination material, newsletters and public deliverables.

Website performance

In order to assess how well the website is reaching stakeholders and acting as a source of information, we use standard web traffic analysis tool (Google Analytics) to track the number of visitors and similar metrics over the life of the project.

Figure 7. Google Analytics – Audience overview 2020

In the above figure, the results from the second reporting period (M13-M24) are presented with an audience overview. The terms used in this figure as well as the results are described here:

- 20,713 Sessions. A session is the period time a user is actively engaged with your website, app, etc. All usage data (Screen Views, Events, Ecommerce, etc.) is associated with a session.
- 13,618 Users. Users have initiated at least one session during the date range.

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- 47,728 Page Views. Pageviews include the total number of pages viewed. Repeated views of a single page are counted.

Figure 12 shows that increased traffic performed during the months May to June and September to November when different training sessions were available for registration including the DOCC.

Figure 8. Google Analytics - Landing pages per pageviews

In addition, the project website statistics show that considerable traffic comes from social media, organic reach and direct links to the project website. The main social media channels that drive the traffic are Facebook, Twitter and LinkedIn while YouTube follows.

Figure 9. Google Analytics - Acquisition overview

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Figure 10. Google Analytics – Main traffic channels

Overall, the promotion and communication of the project and its activities was successful, especially since the main aim was to showcase and attract audience for its training sessions, which were the most popular urls as shown in the figures above.

4.2 Social media and online channels

Social media channels are an integral part of our communication and dissemination strategy as they provide the chance to get connected and reach regions and stakeholders all over the world. The aim of this section is to present the basic elements of the social media strategy and the results of the second reporting period (M13-M24) per social media channel.

Facebook

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Figure 11. GE Academy – Facebook Page

GE Academy has a Facebook page (<https://www.facebook.com/GEAcademy.eu/>) which currently counts 470 followers. According to the figure below, the audience of the page is coming mainly from the project partners countries (Greece, Italy, Germany, Hungary, Czech Republic, Belgium, etc.) and 63% of the followers are women, while men represent the 35%.

Figure 12. Facebook page – Audience breakdown

Twitter

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GE Academy has a Twitter account (https://twitter.com/GEAcademy_eu) which currently counts 962 followers.

Figure 13. GE Academy – Twitter account

According to its analytics, Twitter account offers the biggest visibility in comparison with the other project channels. The number of followers, impressions, reshares and clicks on the different tweet links indicates a good number of engagement, which is visible in the following figures. Specifically, months April, June, July, September and November 2020, numbers are high.

Figure 14. Analytics of indicative popular months

While, during a 90 days period, the account earned 41.1K impressions with over 86 link clicks.

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Figure 15. 90 days overview – Twitter analytics

LinkedIn

GE Academy has a LinkedIn account (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/18976416/>) and a LinkedIn private group to get in touch with the professional network. According to the LinkedIn analytics, GE Academy's account is followed by researchers, people in higher education, etc. which are among the target audiences of GE Academy's training sessions.

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Figure 16. GE Academy on LinkedIn

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Figure 17. LinkedIn Analytics – Followers main industries and locations

YouTube Analytics

Figure 18. YouTube channel analytics part I

GE Academy’s YouTube channel was developed during the first year of the project. At the moment, ten (10) videos have been uploaded. According to the analytics, the videos received more than 1.6K views while the watch time is more than 119 hours. The channel counts 150 subscribers.

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Figure 19. YouTube channel analytics part II

4.3 External events and meetings

Due to the covid-19 pandemic, there were limited opportunities to present GE Academy during external events and meetings. The following efforts were completed for this reporting period:

High-Level Conference “PARTICIPATION OF WOMEN IN THE LABOUR MARKET – BENEFIT FOR THE SOCIETY!”

Date: 31 January 2020 | Location: Zagreb, Croatia | Attended by: YW

The topic of the conference organized by the Croatian Presidency of the EU Council was the (in)equality of women in the labour market: despite positive steps, equality has still not been achieved. Human rights advocate for the protection and promotion of gender equality, a key EU value, by fostering women participation in the labour market and economic independence, seeking sustainable economic growth and development. More info can be found here: <https://ravnopravnost.gov.hr/vijesti/konferencija-visoke-razine-sudjelovanje-zena-na-trzistu-rada-drustvena-dobit-3342/3342>

UN Women Training Centre's Webinar “Online Methodologies and Training for Gender Equality”

Date: 22 July 2020 | Location: Online | Attended by: YW

This Virtual Dialogue was a timely chance to discuss how online methodologies can help us deliver transformative training for gender equality in the context of COVID-19 – and beyond.

Video available on YouTube:

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=W3ljKYyW5iM&ab_channel=UNWomenTrainingCentre

Gender equality in CEE countries: Policies and practices 2020

Date: 13 November 2020 | Location: Online | Attended by: CEU

International conference of “Gender equality in CEE countries: Policies and practices 2020: Institutional change through implementation of GEPs at the RPOs and RFOs in the CEE countries” organized by the Lithuanian Social Research Centre and the Vilnius University where Andrea Krizsan presented “Institutionalizing gender equality at the Central European University”. More info can be found here: <https://www.lstc.lt/en/program/>

H2020 SwafS Calls workshop: from H2020 to Horizon Europe

Date: 29 November 2019 (this event was not reported in the previous report) | Location: Paris, France | Attended by: CNRS

Oral presentation on the SwafS projects as CNRS' Gender Equality unit (Gender-Net Plus & GE Academy). Details provided on the project as well as dissemination elements (social media accounts & website). More info can be found here:

https://cache.media.education.gouv.fr/file/Science-avec-et-pour-la-Societe/03/5/Journee_SwafS_Programme_1209035.pdf

4.4 Newsletter and Press Releases

Currently, seven (7) newsletters have been developed and shared with the GE Academy community, while the mailing list has more than 650 subscribers. We use MailChimp as the platform to develop our newsletters. The published campaigns are listed below:

- [Welcome Newsletter \(Issue I\)](#)
- [Train-the-Trainers session in Berlin and other training opportunities \(Issue II\)](#)
- [Help us co-create the GE Academy online course \(Issue III\)](#)
- [Creating your Gender Equality Plan and other training opportunities \(Issue IV\)](#)
- [Join the Distributed Open Collaborative Course of the Gender Equality Academy](#)
- [New learning opportunities \(Issue VI\)](#)
- [This December is full of learning opportunities \(Issue VII\)](#)

The newsletters include information about i) the project, ii) announcements of training sessions, iii) collaborations with sister projects, iv) and other opportunities to get involved with the community.

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Engagement

Figure 20. Mailchimp analytics

On the occasion of the promotion of the training sessions, press releases are produced and disseminated through various channels from all partners and the partner organisations to run a local promotion attracting participants nationwide.

Dear readers,

We hope this email finds you healthy and safe! We are coming with a newsletter full of learning opportunities.

Starting from a webinar on "[Gender bias in academic recruitment and promotion: Recognizing and overcoming it](#)" tomorrow, closing with an online training on "[Participatory methods for gender equality in science](#)", this is a newsletter recapping all the activities of the GE Academy until the end of this year (while we are working intensively for the delivery of more sessions for 2021!). More information will be found below.

If you are interested or you know someone that would make a great fit for our sessions, continue reading this newsletter for further information or make sure to send it to those interested. We really appreciate the interest in our programme!

The GE Academy team

Title: Gender Equality Academy
Grant Agreement number: 824585
Funding scheme: CSA - Coordination & support action

PRESS RELEASE

Gender Equality Academy announces its first FREE, self-paced online course on "Gender Equality in Research & Innovation: the journey towards Institutional Change"

Thessaloniki, 16 June 2020

The GE Academy team is glad to welcome you in its first Distributed Open Collaborative Course! This highly interactive online learning programme aims at condensing in an online format the best available knowledge and expertise on **Gender Equality in Research and Innovation** stemming from the GE Academy partners and an extended network of contributing nodes and projects from across Europe.

The DOCC format is based on three main features: social, open, and collaborative.

- **Social:** you will have the opportunity to interact with your peers and with the experts all along the course and through different tools that you will find in the LMS platform.
- **Open:** besides permitting an unlimited number of participants, it will always be free of access for everyone.
- **Collaborative:** the course curriculum is the result of a joint effort from some of the main experts of Gender Equality in Europe.

Figure 21. Examples of a newsletter and a Press Release

Both newsletters and press releases are published on the project website: <https://ge-academy.eu/press-kit/>

4.5 Synergies with other projects and initiatives

GE Academy has placed particular efforts in the engagement of relevant stakeholders creating strategic partnerships even from the proposal's level. Having a strong consortium, well-known in the European community, the project has implemented a series of joint activities with the so

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called “sister projects” funded under the H2020 framework and with other gender related initiatives throughout Europe. These projects act as an anchor to different EU Member states and widening countries offering the chance of organising local training sessions and capitalising on their local networks to widespread the word about GE Academy and having more organisations sensitised and participating in our capacity building programme.

Figure 22. GE Academy synergies in a nutshell

GE Academy created the webpage “Synergies” (<https://ge-academy.eu/synergies/>) showcasing the community.

Some of the activities that have taken place during this reporting period are listed below (the list is non-exhaustive):

- GE Academy is a proud member of Eurogender (<https://eurogender.eige.europa.eu/users/gender-equality-academy>) (powered by the [European Institute of Gender Equality](#) (EIGE), an online consultation and cooperation platform). GE Academy uploads its news and events via the platform to notify the community.
- GE Academy organised its second workshop “Dealing with resistances” in Barcelona, Spain in cooperation with the [ACT project](#). ACT project produced a video featuring Dr. Lucy Ferguson, GE Academy’s trainer (<https://vimeo.com/422450395>).
- GE Academy is in continuous liaison with the communication team of [Gearing Roles](#) for cross-promoting content for both projects. In addition, GE Academy is featured on the Gearing Roles website (<https://gearingroles.eu/sister-projects/>), while YW team attended its conference. Lastly, Gearing Roles partners Anne Laure Humbert and Simonetta Manfredi from the Oxford Brookes University participated in the 2nd webinar of GE Academy presenting the following topic: "Women and Innovation: the case of

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University spinout companies". In addition, a joint webinar was organised (M16) and it will be reported in the next reporting period.

- GE Academy partners attended the final conference of [EQUAL-IST](#) and presented the project. In addition, GE Academy was featured on its newsletters.
- GE Academy was featured in one of the project's newsletters with an interview from Lut Mergaert and Vasiliki Madesi (<https://ge-academy.eu/ge-uploads/2019/09/4th-GEECCO-Newsletter.pdf>), while Amaia Lusa Garcia, UPC, professor of Industrial Engineering presented the topic: "Gender Equality at Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya" during the 1st webinar of GE Academy.
- [GENDER-SMART](#) representatives participated in the in-person training "How to avoid gender bias in recruitment and promotion?"
- [Supera project](#) representatives participated in the in-person training "How to avoid gender bias in recruitment and promotion?"
- GE Academy collaborates with various projects and initiatives for the development of the DOCC content ([Gearing Roles](#), [GEECCO](#), [Gender Smart EU](#), [Caliper project](#), [Diamond EU project](#), [GEWINN](#), [EFFORTI](#), [DomEQUAL](#)).
- Joint communication campaigns have been organised in at least two occasions using the hash tag #COMMIT2GENDERRING on Twitter:
 - the International Women's Day;
 - leadership campaign;

4.6 Promotion through partners' networks

Partners use their own social media accounts to disseminate the project and its activities. The rationale is that partners have already thousands of followers in social media and trust is already established between them and their followers. Partners are tagged in project announcements and posts and their reshares help the project to achieve a bigger visibility. According to the monitoring form, the contribution of partners is shown below:

Figure 23. Promotion through partners' networks

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A few examples can be found below:

Figure 24. Smart Venice sample posts about GE Academy

Figure 25. TU Dublin sample post about GE Academy

In addition, partners upload information about the project on their website pages and their newsletters.

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Figure 26. GE Academy training session on K-RCN newsletter

5. Monitoring and evaluation

As the actions of GE Academy are increasing and the reach of the project is steadily growing, it is necessary to keep track of the communication and dissemination activities of partners in a more accurate form. The project adopted a standardized reporting procedure, which will be valuable in order to assess the efficiency of the consortium in terms of promoting GE Academy's actions and achieving the projected impact. To allow an adequate monitoring of the communication and dissemination activities and understand the impact generated by these activities, partners are requested to report their relevant actions carried out using a specific reporting template (see Annex I). In addition, specific performance indicators have been developed from the beginning of the project in order to allow comparisons between the planned and actual activities as well as their effectiveness to reach their goals.

This deliverable provides an overview of the communication and dissemination activities during year 2, while this section presents the relevant key performance indicators and their progress.

5.1 Key Performance Indicators

The table below provides a summary of the project online and offline performance, which is considered sufficient taking into account the preparation phase during year 1 as well as the use of the partners' online and offline channels as key dissemination tools. These numbers are expected to significantly increase during the second project year particularly due to the initiation of the roll-out phase of the GE Academy's programme, thus reaching and exceeding the target values of the project.

Key Performance Indicator (KPI)	Target value (M36)	Current status (M24)
Social Media		
No. of Twitter followers	600	962
No. of likes on Facebook	400	470
No. of Project videos	5	10
No. of views on YouTube	200 per video	1,628 total views
Website		
No. of accesses per year	2000	47,728
No. of downloads of deliverables	300	83 downloads Deliverables were recently uploaded on the project website as their approval was

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		pending from the EC. Thus, the number is lower than expected but it will be higher next year.
No. of individuals / organisations signed up to receive email updates on project progress	150 by M24 300 by M36	650 subscribers
Peer reviewed scientific papers, conference publications & policy briefs		
No. of manuscripts accepted for publication	2	n/a This task starts at a later stage
No. of policy briefs / white papers	2	n/a This task starts at a later stage
Events, conferences (Public awareness and sharing of experience with external experts in the field)		
Participation in conferences and workshops	10	7(2019) 4 (2020) Total: 11
Distribution of leaflets in events	at least 500	This is postponed due to covid-19

6. Conclusions and lessons-learnt

This is the second reporting deliverable, and it provides an update of the project's dissemination and communication strategy and reports the progress achieved so far towards engaging its target groups. The deliverable covers the period between M13 to M24 flagged by the reassess of the strategy towards the promotion of the training sessions, the roll-out programme and the covid-19 pandemic. This phase enabled the project partners to intensify the dissemination activities through the promotion of the project online training sessions.

The lessons-learnt during this period include:

- Acting as local ambassadors is the most effective communication tactic. The regional networks of each Partner are very valuable to this cause. Thus, Partners should give emphasis in engaging with the community and the stakeholders of their region. The role of local promoting partners in online training sessions is very important in reaching out to certain areas and organisations.
- Adapting the wording to local needs and straightforward titles is the most effective way of communication and engagement.
- Optimal online content is key for the engagement with potential participants to online sessions and training sessions
- With our current channels and messages, men are not engaged as much as women.

Overall, the results of this period (M13-M24) are more than satisfactory since all the goals and targets were achieved:

- More than 962 followers on Twitter while the overall project goal (M36) is 600 followers.
- More than 470 likes and follows on Facebook, while the overall project goal is 400 likes.
- The number of subscribers on the project newsletter has been achieved from this first year, while this number will be increased the following years with an overall number of 650 subscribers.
- Participation and promotion of GE Academy in more than 4 relevant events and conferences.
- More than 47,728 pages views on the project website with 13,689 users were achieved.
- The target number of registrations and participants to the training sessions was achieved, while in the cases that this was not achieved lessons-learnt and mitigation measures have been adopted and will be implemented the following year.

To sum up, all the expected results for this period have been reached. The efforts managed to achieve more than expected and created a strong network of GE Academy followers which is still expanding. The results of this period give us the confidence to engage with more people and relevant groups and achieve even greater results for the following critical year of the roll-out programme and the sustainability activities.

7. Annex

Annex I: Communication and Dissemination Reporting

The form is available via this link: <https://forms.gle/E3Esgkkf7nFa5Eaj9> It is used as an easy-to-use tool to report any communication and dissemination activities. Partners are able to choose their organisation, the type of the activity (the list is based on the ECAS portal) and upload any relevant attachments.

